

1 Monocular Kilometer-Scale Passive Ranging 2 by Point-Spread Function Engineering

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13 **Abstract**

14 Standard imaging systems are designed for 2D representation of objects, while information
15 about the third dimension remains implicit, as imaging-based distance estimation is a difficult
16 challenge. Existing long-range distance estimation technologies mostly rely on active emission
17 of signal, which as a subsystem, constitutes a significant portion of the complexity, size and
18 cost of the active-ranging apparatus. Despite the appeal of alleviating the requirement for
19 signal-emission, passive distance estimation methods are essentially nonexistent for ranges
20 greater than a few hundreds of meters. Here, we present monocular long-range, telescope-based
21 passive ranging, realized by integration of point-spread-function engineering into a telescope,
22 extending the scale of point-spread-function engineering-based ranging to distances where it
23 has never been tested before. We provide experimental demonstrations of the optical system in
24 a variety of challenging imaging scenarios, including adversarial weather conditions, dynamic
25 targets and scenes of diversified textures, at distances extending beyond 1.7 km. We conclude
26 with brief quantification of the effect of atmospheric turbulence on estimation precision, which
27 becomes a significant error source in long-range optical imaging.

28

29 **1. Introduction**

30 From microscopy to astronomy, depth estimation is a challenging task in optics due to difficulty
31 of encoding three-dimensional (3D) information in a two-dimensional (2D) image. Spanning
32 scales from nanometers to light-years, the requirement for depth estimation, namely, ranging,
33 covers a variety of applications and has yielded numerous imaging schemes. At the scale of
34 tens of meters to kilometers, ranging is especially essential in the fields of autonomous vehicles,
35 defense, and aircraft landing systems. Most common techniques make use of active
36 measurements. Such measurements, e.g. radar or LIDAR, rely upon detection of a signal
37 returning from the ranged objects. This requires emission of intense signals, often making the
38 measurement system bulky and expensive, or unsuitable for some applications due to safety or
39 source-detectability constraints. Additionally, active ranging that is based on individual lines
40 of sight (e.g. LIDAR) require scanning and may be rendered unreliable in the presence of even
41 scarce amounts of dust particles in the air[1], due to back-scattering.

42 Passive ranging methods, on the other hand, benefit from relying solely on incoming optical
43 signal. Traditional methods such as depth from focus/defocus[2], or triangulation by stereo
44 imaging[3] are usually limited in their application to rather short distances. In fact, to the best
45 of our knowledge such methods have not been applied at distances far surpassing 100-200

46 meters[4], although efforts in this direction have been made[5]. A fundamental limitation
47 common to these methods stems from their dependence on highly accurate feature detection or
48 blur estimation, which become inefficient at larger distances, where atmospheric turbulence
49 (AT) comes into play. Another drawback associated with the focus/defocus approaches is that
50 they require multiple frames under different camera settings, which usually involves
51 mechanically moving parts. Stereo vision relies on two or more viewpoints[6], with challenges
52 including the need for precise feature detection, as well as the bulkiness of an apparatus with
53 two optical systems, and stringent cross-channel registration requirements. A different
54 approach for ranging at such range scales makes use of signal degradation due to long
55 propagation through the atmosphere – the effects of absorption, scattering and turbulence
56 increase with distance, thus hold useful information[7,8]. The downside of such approaches is
57 that due to unknown atmosphere properties, they require *a priori* information, such as the
58 properties of the imaged scene, or the existence of a reference object at a known distance.

59 Another approach for distance estimation is wavefront shaping, specifically, point-spread-
60 function (PSF) engineering; it is implemented by modifying the light-path to the sensor in order
61 to change the optical system’s PSF[9–11], namely, the image that a point source generates in
62 the detector plane. The modified PSF contains information on the curvature of the incoming
63 wavefront, encoding the distance of the object. The versatility of the wavefront shaping
64 approach lies in the ability to design the PSF per application – the PSF can capture distance for
65 three-dimensional imaging[11–14], extend imaging depth of field[15], encode color[16–19],
66 correct aberrations[20,21] and more.

67 Here, we present a monocular approach for long-distance ranging, based on PSF
68 engineering in a telescope. Combining optical wavefront shaping with decoding algorithms
69 enables us to demonstrate single-shot ranging of moving objects and real-world scenes at
70 distances surpassing 1.7 km. We provide quantitative results obtained by analytical as well as
71 deep neural-network based image analysis, and discuss the sources of error that bound system
72 performance.

73

74 2. Materials and methods

75 2.1 Wavefront shaping and cepstrum analysis

76 Our optical system is based on a commercial telescope, augmented by a 4-f extension providing
77 easy access to the Fourier plane. There, a diffractive optical element modulates the wavefront,
78 consequently encoding depth information into the PSF (Fig. 1). Extraction of PSF information
79 from a general, unknown continuous image is a difficult challenge due to the convoluted
80 process of image formation. We explore two depth-decoding techniques: a center-of-mass
81 (CoM) based analytical approach and a neural-net based approach. The decoding method is
82 inspired by previous related work by Berlich et al.[14], where the double-helix PSF[10,22] was
83 used to estimate distance at short ranges (~1 m). With the double-helix PSF, the camera
84 measures a convolution between a sharp image and the PSF comprising two lobes with
85 orientation determined by the distance of the imaged object (Fig. 1). This image can be regarded
86 to as one subject to an echo – a translated replica of the base signal. The decoding challenge is
87 to recover the direction of the echo from the measured image, which entails the object distance.
88 A useful mathematical tool to identify echoes in a signal is the complex cepstrum[23] (denoted
89 from now on simply as cepstrum) - \mathcal{C} , defined as:

$$90 \quad \mathcal{C} = \mathcal{F}^{-1}(\ln(\mathcal{F}(I))) \quad (1)$$

91 where I is an image, \mathcal{F} is the Fourier-transform operator, and \ln denotes the natural logarithm
 92 operator. Given an image containing a single echo of translation x_r , the cepstrum would
 93 contain a train of impulses following the same direction as x_r [24]. Upon finding the direction
 94 of the impulses in the cepstrum, the distance of the object in the image can be resolved. In
 95 practice, typically only two lobes from the train are visible. In the analytical approach, distance
 96 estimation is achieved by locating each lobe's center-of-mass, calculating lobe orientation and
 97 comparing with a distance-to-angle calibration curve. In the neural net-based decoding
 98 approach, a neural net is trained to receive the cepstrum and output object distance (see 2.4.2
 99 and SI for details).

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Fig. 1. Optical setup and analysis pipeline. A) Optical setup, comprising of a telescope and a subsequent 4-f system; WF – incoming light wavefront, T-telescope BP – Bandpass filter, L – Lens, PM – phase mask. b. Simulated PSFs of the optical system, at different distances. c. Analysis pipeline of distance estimation: (1) The Cepstrum transform (CT) is applied on an ROI in the image. (2) The cepstrum is filtered to improve lobe detection. (3) A window is chosen around the maximal-value pixel, and Center of Mass (CoM) localization is performed inside. (4) The angle of the CoM is obtained, and used to estimate distance, based on a calibration curve (details in Materials and Methods). d. Illustration of the alternative depth-decoding process by a neural network

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102 Note that the cepstrum is affected by scene content; this can be understood by examining
 103 two extreme cases – the first is an object containing no features at all – e.g. a plain wall or clear
 104 sky. Any modification to the PSF of such a scene would introduce no change to the measured
 105 image, thus we will not observe any impulses in the cepstrum. The second extreme case is a
 106 signal that contains repetitive features in a distinct direction, such as a fence or window shutters.
 107 Such features in the image appear as an echo which will dominate the PSF-related impulse and
 108 could lead to incorrect distance estimation.

109

110 *2.2 The Optical system*

111 We implemented a PSF-engineering optical system comprising a telescope objective lens and
112 a 4-f extension, to access the Fourier plane, where a diffractive optical element modulates the
113 wavefront. A large light-gathering area is essential in order to maximize the information carried
114 by the wavefront, thus we used an off-the-shelf telescope (Astromaster 102AZ, aperture
115 diameter: 102 mm, $f=660$ mm) as the objective lens. We removed the eyepiece module and
116 placed an optical 4-f extension instead, held onto the telescope by a custom-made 3D printed
117 mount. In the 4-f extension, we used a pair of CCTV lenses (Kowa LM50FC24M, $f = 50$ mm),
118 as we found standard achromatic lenses to suffer from a significant FOV dependent aberration,
119 which appears to be Petzval field curvature. In the Fourier plane of the extension, we placed a
120 photolithography-etched phase mask. Additionally, we placed a spectral bandpass filter
121 (Chroma AT565/30) to optimize PSF engineering performance. Images were captured by FLIR
122 grasshopper 3 camera (GS3-U3-120S6M-C).

123 2.3 Phase mask design

124 The phase mask of choice was inspired by previous work by Berlich et al.[14], where the
125 double-helix PSF[10] was used to estimate distance in a macroscale scene. The goal PSF
126 comprises of two lobes (ideally – two delta functions), rotating about their middle point as a
127 function of object distance (Fig 1.B). To produce such a PSF, a proper phase mask needs to be
128 designed, manufactured and placed in the optical system. To design the phase mask, a synthetic
129 set of 2D realizations of the desired PSF was generated, with each realization corresponding a
130 defined object distance. In line with the PSF requirement, each realization comprised of a pair
131 of 2D Gaussians separated by a fixed distance and oriented at an angle depending on object
132 distance. Specifically, orientation angle changed linearly with one-over-the distance, which has
133 proven to produce the most efficient results, as expected from the properties of optical
134 wavefront propagation. Once generating the synthetic 2D-PSFs and corresponding object
135 distances, Vectorial-Implementation of Phase Retrieval[25] was implemented to obtain the
136 pupil phase that generates a PSF similar to the synthetic set. The obtained pupil phase describes
137 the phase mask required for the desired PSF (the resulting phase is color-coded in the top-right
138 circle in Fig 1.A). Based on the optimized phase design, a quartz phase mask was fabricated by
139 photolithography, as described previously[19,26].

140 2.4 Image processing

141 2.4.1 Complex cepstrum – CoM-based analysis

142 The cepstrum domain is degraded due to the unknown object feature content, imaging noise
143 and the shape of the PSF, which comprise of two lobes, rather than a pair of highly localized
144 impulses. This required us to perform a series of steps in order to accurately allocate the
145 impulses in the cepstrum, as shown in Fig. 1.C. The process of obtaining the lobe-angles is as
146 follows: Initially, we apodize in the ROI prior to cepstrum calculation, by multiplying the ROI
147 by a Hann windowing function. This is done to reduce artificial vertical and horizontal lines to
148 the cepstrum, which we wish to avoid.

149 Next, the cepstrum was calculated according to Eq. 1. Cepstrums from multiple images
150 were then averaged, if needed (e.g. for system calibration). At this point, the cepstrum generally
151 comprises of the two lobes, in addition to lines that intersect the center, in cases where
152 continuous lines appear in the raw image. The goal is to find a proper window around one of
153 the lobes, and to perform a CoM localization inside it. To avoid the center-intersecting lines,
154 we multiplied the cepstrums by a weight matrix W , that enhances regions that have strong
155 gradients in the radial direction, while oppressing regions of strong tangential gradients. To
156 generate W , the cepstrum is blurred (Gaussian filtering with $\sigma = 2$ for all analysis except drone,
157 for which $\sigma = 3$) and the gradients (both magnitude, G_m and direction, G_ϕ) are calculated. G_m
158 is smoothed by a median filter, and the projection of the gradient on the radial direction is raised
159 to a high power α , to obtain our weight function:

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$$W_\rho(\rho, \varphi) = \cos(\varphi - G_\varphi(\rho, \varphi))^\alpha \quad (2)$$

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where (ρ, φ) are the radial and angular polar coordinates of the matrix, w_ρ is a weight matrix

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based on the gradients' radial projection. Throughout analysis, we used $\alpha=4$. The motivation

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for using w_ρ is to suppress regions where intense gradients appear that are mainly tangential,

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as in the case of the center-intersecting lines. The final weight matrix W is obtained by

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multiplying the gradient magnitude matrix G_m by w_ρ , to maintain regions containing strong

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gradients in the radial direction, and applying a Gaussian blur. Once W is generated, it

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multiplies the original cepstrum (element-wise), and the product is further blurred. The result

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is multiplied by a binary map of a ring around the center, to avoid any high-intensity pixels that

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are not the correct distance from the cepstrum center. Finally, the maximal pixel (x_0, y_0) is

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chosen as the center of the window. The ring-shaped map is defined to be 6 pixels wide around

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the expected distance of the lobe, which is constant for all distances as determined by the PSF.

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For CoM calculation, the original cepstrum is smoothed by a median filter, then a window about

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(x_0, y_0) is cropped. Inside it, a threshold is applied to reduce the sensitivity of the localization

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to choice of window position[27]. Finally, the CoM is calculated inside the window, leading to

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a value of θ – the angle where the lobe is centered; if the CoM is more than 1 pixel away from

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the center, the window center is updated according to the result and the CoM is calculated in

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the new window.

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2.4.2 Complex cepstrum – Neural-network-based analysis

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In addition to the analytical approach, we applied a convolutional neural network to decode

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distance from cepstrum. Network training was performed using cepstrums of simulated images,

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which were generated in four steps: 1. convolving a sharp telescope image with a PSF obtained

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from a revised imaging model (corresponding a known distance), 2. applying an apodization to

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the convolved image to alleviate the cross lines in cepstrums, 3. calculating the cepstrum; and

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finally, 4. removing the cepstrum center to solely address the side-lobes, that contain the

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meaningful information. Imperatively, for the network to correctly estimate distance of real

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data, high consistency must be achieved between the simulated PSF and the actual PSF of the

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optical system. The latter is expected to differ from the theoretical one (obtained from the

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phase-mask design) due to phase-mask manufacturing errors, misalignments and optics-

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induced aberrations. The degraded experimental PSF requires a revised optical system

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characterization, which we obtain via a process of phase retrieval (PR) process [28]

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(specifically, Misell algorithm[29]).

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For the PR process, the PSF was measured at 12 known distances, by imaging a bright

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point-like light source under minimal turbulence conditions. To better account for nonzero

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turbulence, 100 frames were acquired per distance, producing multiple slightly-perturbed

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realizations of the optical-system's PSF. In brief, the process of PR involves iterative

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estimations of the wavefront at the pupil plane of the 4-f extension (the plane of the phase

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mask), and the image plane. Using the optical model and measured PSFs, phase at the pupil

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plane is iteratively updated until converging to the true pupil plane of the optical system, which

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fully describes the PSF. Per iteration, a random set of frames (one frame per distance, out of

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the 100 acquired) was used, in order to average out the effect of random turbulence on the

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retrieved phase. We have found both in simulations and in experiments, that as long as

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turbulence severity is below a certain level, PR converges to a stable solution. More detail on

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PR is found in the SI.

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The neural net includes a feature detection part and a regression part. The former is used to

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obtain higher-level features of the input cepstrum, e.g. lobe positions. It consists of 4

206 convolution blocks/layers, each of which is made up of three consecutive convolution
207 operations followed by batch normalization and ReLU nonlinear operation, and a max pooling
208 at the end. The outputs of those 4 blocks have channel number of 32, 64, 128 and 256
209 respectively. Then a global pooling is applied to reduce both the height and width to 1. The
210 regression part is a fully connected layer with Sigmoid as the activation function aiming to
211 predict distance from the higher-level features. We apply the relative L1 norm as the loss
212 function:

$$213 \quad Loss = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{|\hat{y}_i - y_i|}{y_i + \varepsilon} \quad (3)$$

214 where \hat{y}_i, y_i , and N are the network prediction, ground truth, and batch size (128),
215 respectively, and $\varepsilon = 1$ is a regularization constant.

216 *2.5 Data acquisition*

217 *2.5.1 Car distance measurement*

218 Data was acquired on March the 1st, 2022, at 16:00. Temperatures were around 17.5°C and
219 winds of around 10 km/h. Exposure time was 120 ms to account for low light conditions, as the
220 car was driving west on sunset, with 200 ms between frames.

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222 *2.5.2 Drone distance measurement*

223 Data was acquired on April the 19th 2022, near Haifa in the morning. The weather was hot
224 (~31°C) with moderate winds (~13 km/h). Exposure times were between 6.5 ms to 11 ms,
225 depending on the sky brightness due to clouds. Viewed from the front, the size of the drone is
226 31.8×26.7 cm². Outliers were excluded using mean absolute deviation (Matlab isoutlier
227 function default), no more than 10 outliers were excluded per distance.

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229 *2.5.3 Static scene – clear day*

230 Data was acquired on the 25th of March 2022 at noon. Temperatures were around 12°C with
231 wind of 18 km/h. Exposure times were determined by object brightness (albedo and
232 illumination). Exact values are specified in Table S1. Outliers were excluded using mean
233 absolute deviation, and are shown in Fig. 3.C.

234 *2.5.4 Static scene – dusty weather*

235 Data was acquired on the 25th of April 2022 at the afternoon. Temperature was 21.7°C with
236 low winds (<5 km/h). Exposure time was 60 ms, with gain of 5 dB.

237 *2.5.5 Turbulence measurements*

238 Data was acquired on April the 18th, 2022 at time intervals of approximately one hour, from
239 10:00 to 20:00. The weather that day measured temperatures between 18.7-34°C with wind
240 speeds peaking at 34 km/h.

241 *2.6 System calibration*

242 Calibration in our context is the process of establishing the relation between the lobe angle in
243 the cepstrum and object distance. It was done by imaging a set of scenes containing objects

244 having a well-known distance across the sensor (e.g. large walls with a planar depth map). For
 245 calibration, a large number of frames was acquired per scene. Each scene was divided to a grid
 246 of partially overlapping ROIs, with a single ground truth (GT) distance assigned to each ROI.
 247 Next, cepstrums were calculated per ROI, per frame, and then averaged in non-consecutive
 248 groups of 5 to improve the contrast prior to the lobe seeking. After obtaining the mean PSF-
 249 angle per ROI in each of the scenes, a calibration between angle and distance was fitted using
 250 the ROI lobe-angles and GT distances (see next paragraphs). Three fitted parameters per ROI
 251 determine the relation between PSF-angle and distance, locally. As a final step, 2nd degree 2D
 252 polynomials were fitted to each of the parameters across the FOV, to generate FOV-dependent
 253 calibration curves.

254 The relation between the PSF-angles in the cepstrum and distance, per ROI, was established
 255 experimentally by fitting local curves following the theoretical relation between these entities.
 256 This relation is based on the conjunction that the angle of the PSF is inversely proportional to
 257 the distance, according to our phase-mask design.

258 This conjunction leads to a generalized relation between the angle θ and distance z ,

$$259 \quad \theta = a + \frac{b}{z - c} \quad (4)$$

260 where a, b, c are the fit parameters. a represents the lobe angle at $z \rightarrow \infty$, b defines the
 261 sensitivity of the angle to change in distance and c is the distance corresponding the asymptote
 262 $\theta \rightarrow \infty$

263 Rewriting for z we get:

$$264 \quad z = c + \frac{b}{\theta - a} \quad (5)$$

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266 3. Results

267 3.1 Dynamic object distance estimation

268 To demonstrate the applicability of our approach to range determination from a moving
 269 object, we imaged a car driving along a straight road extending nearly 800 m. Per frame, an
 270 ROI confined within the car boundaries was chosen. The ROI size was chosen to be 247^2 pixels,
 271 based on the apparent size of the car at its farthest position from the camera. As a rule of thumb,
 272 cepstrum analysis performed on larger ROIs reduces noise and leads to improved precision.
 273 We generated a calibration function relating cepstrum lobe-angle, which is the PSF angle, to
 274 distance, prior to the acquisition. The calibration was made in a Field-of-View (FOV)
 275 dependent manner (see 2.6 for further details), to account for a minor effect of FOV-dependence
 276 of the PSF which was observed. We suspect this effect to originate from the telescope lens, as
 277 we are pushing the viewing angles farther than the design FOV of the telescope. Using the
 278 calibration, the PSF angle of an ROI inside the car was used to estimate the distance of the car
 279 per frame, using both our analytical CoM method and the neural-net method. As a validation,
 280 we evaluated the Ground Truth (GT) distance of the car per frame by application of prior
 281 knowledge, namely, by knowing the “track width” of the car (defined as the distance between
 282 the back wheels of the car) and that it moves away from the observer in a smooth fashion. Using
 283 the track width, the apparent magnification was calculated per frame, from which distance was
 284 derived. The error in GT values is estimated at 1.5%. Details of GT evaluation process and
 285 discussion of errors are in the SI.

286 The results in Fig. 2 show that the passive-ranging estimation complies with the GT, while
 287 the absolute error increases with distance. Throughout the motion, the single-shot error

288 (deviation from GT) was calculated; average error was found to be 3.4% of GT for the CoM
289 analysis, and 6.0% for the net, and remains typically below 10% for the duration of the motion.
290 Nevertheless, we can observe two trends in the error (Fig. 2.D). The first is the decrease in
291 precision with increasing distance. This is due to the reduced sensitivity of wavefront curvature
292 to distance, and plausibly due to an increased contribution of AT as light travels a larger
293 distance through the air. The second observable effect is finite accuracy, manifested as a bias
294 (different slope) between the trend lines of estimated distances, in either of the analysis
295 approaches, and the GT curve. This originates from finite mechanical stability of parts in the
296 system (e.g. a PLA 3D-printed connection between the optics and the telescope frame), leading
297 to small variations in system calibration when transported between experiment sites. Error that
298 originates from bias is not native to the method, suggesting performance can improve upon
299 using robust, metallic components.

300 We also demonstrated dynamic aerial object ranging, by measuring the distance to a drone
301 (DJI Mavic Mini), at several distances up to 1.08 km. Per distance, 100 frames were acquired.
302 At large distances, the object was smaller than the PSF lobes separation, thus it appeared as two
303 objects, shifted at the PSF angle corresponding the distance (Fig. 2.G). By employing the
304 cepstrum approach the PSF angles and the distances were extracted.

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306 *3.2 Static object distance estimation*

307 Another appealing use of our method is passive, single-shot ranging of static objects. To
308 demonstrate this application, we acquired images centered on 27 different objects (e.g. trees,
309 walls, cars) spread across a large view (Fig. 3.A). Per object, 100 frames were acquired for the
310 purpose of precision analysis. Range estimation was performed using the analytical method,
311 and results were evaluated by estimation precision and difference from the GT values. GT
312 distance to objects closer than 1,000 m was measured using a laser rangefinder. Beyond this
313 applicable range of the laser rangefinder, GPS was used for distance determination. We
314 estimate the precision of the rangefinder to be ~1 m, based on a discretization behavior it
315 exhibited, and the precision of our GPS-based determination method to be 5 m. Exposure times
316 were determined per frame to maximize image contrast while avoiding saturation (Table S1).
317 Per frame, the cepstrum was calculated from an ROI of size 401^2 pixels, and the orientation of
318 the PSF was extracted. Of the 27 scenes, a small subset was used for calibration (every 3rd
319 scene by order of acquisition, not displayed in Fig. 3), while the other scenes were used to test
320 the ranging performance. For each calibration scene, the average cepstrum angle of 100 frames
321 was used to generate a calibration curve (Fig S4).

Fig. 2. Results of distance estimation of a driving car. A-C. (Right) Example frames. The analyzed ROI is highlighted in blue. (Top left) The ROI. (Bottom left) A close up of the cepstrum of the lobe is expressed by a line from the center. D. PSF-based estimations compared against a curve generated by applying priors on the data. The results can be seen in detail in Video S1. E. Snapshots of a flying drone at different distances. F. The results of drone distance estimation. GT is obtained from the drone's built-in GPS (assumed precision of ~ 5 m). Standard deviation of distance estimation is based on estimation from 100 individual frames.

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To improve the calibration process, we reduced the effect of unknown scene features over the cepstrum, before lobe-determination. We did so by measuring in parallel an unmodulated, focused image, calculating the average cepstrum of 10 such frames, and subtracting it from the calibration cepstrums. Note that this parallel acquisition was performed only during the calibration step; all subsequent range estimations were done using a single modulated image. Additionally, cepstrums in the calibration data were averaged (in non-consecutive groups of 5) to improve the contrast before finding the lobe-angles. A calibration function was then fitted, relating lobe-angle to GT distance, which was eventually used for distance estimation.

The results of the 18 scenes comprising the test data are presented in Fig. 3 and Table S1. We observed that the lobes in the cepstrum remain clearly visible regardless of distance, and are largely affected by the texture of the scene. The precision of the estimation is reduced as distance increases, mostly due to the decreased sensitivity of the wavefront curvature to distance. We observe bias in several objects - this is primarily due to the contribution of the object features to the cepstrum, which may "pull" the lobes CoM in some direction. The effect is most significant in images that contain repetitive features or continuous lines, such as tiled walls or windows. Generally, if there is a repeating feature in a scene (or a continuous line), where the repetition angle is close to the direction of the PSF orientation, it will bias the CoM localization, affecting the estimated lobe angle. This can be observed in scene K, where a vertical line in the scene overshadows the near-vertical orientation of the cepstrum lobes. In

343 other cases, the cepstral contribution of lines can be ignored if it is sufficiently separated from
 344 the PSF-induced lobes in the cepstrum (e.g. scenes M, Q).

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Fig. 3. Distance estimation of static scenes. **A.** A color image of the view containing the targets used for distance estimation. The ROI of each target is marked by a square. **B.** Results of distance estimation per object, compared to the GT values from the rangefinder or GPS. Error bars indicate the standard deviation in distance estimation, from 100 frames. **C.** Zoom-ins on the ROIs, and their cepstrums. Left images – ROI of each object, as acquired by the PSF-engineering system (first frame is shown). Right images – the average cepstrum of 100 frames, with blue lines indicating the estimated lobe-angle obtained per frame, yellow lines mark excluded outliers. Note that the averaged cepstrum is symmetric, so that the area covered by the lines is mirrored around the center of the cepstrum. **D.** Example scene in acquired in dusty atmosphere. **E.** The image of the scene as acquired by the PSF-engineering setup. ROI zoom-ins and their complementary cepstrums are shown to the right. GT values of the ROIs are 517 m (orange) and 1,130 m (blue), measured with the rangefinder on a clear day. **F.** Depth-map of the scene obtained by patch-based cepstrum analysis. The pixels of the depth map are smaller than the complement ROI sizes due to the

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Continuous lines in the image yield lines that cross the center of the cepstrum and reduce in intensity as the radius increases. Appearance of such line is not uncommon in urban scenes, so we handle these cases algorithmically to only detect the lobes (see 2.4.1). The results show consistency of the angle-distance relation which is maintained over a large range. The precision

351 of the results, calculated from the standard deviation of the angle estimations, is given by the
352 error bars in Fig. 3.B. Another interesting scene is L, containing a concrete wall with essentially
353 no features. This is an extreme example demonstrating the limitation of PSF engineering for
354 ranging of objects with little-or-no texture, as hardly any features are seen in the cepstrum.
355

356 A major advantage of our approach over active range-finding is robustness to back-scatter
357 from nearby scatterers, e.g. dust particles. To validate this, we examined the performance of
358 the system under severe presence of dust in the air. We acquired images of a scene spanning a
359 broad range of distances, and analyzed the depth-map of the scene. We did so by analyzing
360 partially-overlapping ROIs (ROI size of 401^2 pixels, shift between adjacent ROI centers is 125
361 pixels). To account for the poor contrast from the dust, cepstrums from 5 consecutive frames
362 were averaged before lobe-finding. Once found, the PSF angles were translated to distance
363 using a calibration curve. Lastly, a median filter was applied to eliminate outliers, and obtain a
364 depth-map of the scene (Fig. 3.F). Importantly, under such a heavy presence of dust in the air,
365 the laser rangefinder failed to measure any target farther than the tree to the left (reading 458
366 m), repeatedly returning values of 20-30 m (Video S3). Similar results showing robustness to
367 dust were obtained imaging a driving truck (Video S4).

368 *3.3 Atmospheric turbulence and precision*

369 Fluctuations in temperature and pressure of the air, namely, AT, induce random changes to the
370 refractive index of the medium, distorting the wavefront. The effect of AT is clearly visible in
371 long-distance (generally >100 m) imaging, both in traditional in-focus imaging and in our PSF-
372 engineered setup. In traditional imaging, the contribution of AT is local translations across the
373 image, accompanied by a blur due to the degraded PSF (Video S5). In our optical setup, the
374 degraded wavefront (thus PSF) may also lead to false distance estimation.

375 We believe that the main contribution to distance estimation error due to AT occurs by a
376 wavefront curvature aberration (defocus) - other aberrations deform the lobes, introducing
377 noise by lowering contrast. The error introduced by AT is the one we are most concerned with,
378 and we find it to be the bottleneck to the system performance. In order to evaluate the effect of
379 turbulence on distance estimation, we imaged a point light source from a distance of 670 m.
380 The acquisition was made on a hot day, where the peak turbulence was expected to be severe.
381 Each hour, 1,000 frames were acquired under multiple exposure and gain settings, and in each
382 frame the angle of the PSF was calculated by the CoM position of each of the PSF lobes. The
383 effect of AT is apparent when imaging such a solitary point source, scintillating due to
384 turbulence (Fig. 4.A).

385 At around noon, where AT is at its peak, the effect on the angles was eminent. This can be
386 seen by the increased spread of the PSF angles, reaching a standard deviation of PSF angles
387 (σ_θ) of almost 6.5° (Fig. 4.B). As AT-based error can be characterized by σ_θ it can be translated
388 to precision in distance estimation using the system calibration. Fig. 4.C shows the system's
389 single-shot ranging capabilities, providing a given tolerance of ranging precision (5% or 10%).
390 Distance-determination precision can be improved by repeating the estimation over multiple
391 frames; however, it is important to note that sufficient time is required between frames to obtain
392 independence between the measurements, due to the finite correlation time of AT. We
393 measured this effect by calculating the temporal correlation of the error in the different levels
394 of AT (Fig. 4.D), and found that the temporal correlation is between 20-70 ms, defined as the
395 point where normalized correlation decreases to 0.5. Importantly, as one could expect, strong
396 turbulence tends to feature shorter correlation times. The implication is that under strong AT,
397 snapshots acquired with short time separation will improve ranging precision more than the
398 case of weak AT. This provides some amount of counter-effect to the limited precision. During
399 measurements, we did not observe any effect of exposure time or gain levels over the precision,

400 reinforcing the assumption that in our acquisition regime, the AT is the main cause for error,
 401 rather than limited photon count.
 402

403

Fig. 4. Turbulence effect on precision. A. The effect of turbulence on the PSF. PSFs from a point source acquired under mild (light blue, top row) and intense (red, bottom row) turbulence conditions (data from 20:00 and 12:00, respectively). First 3 frames of each data were colored and overlaid to emphasize the effect. The average of all 1,000 frames is shown in grayscale at the rightmost image. B. (Top) Density-plot of the angle-estimation results from 1,000 frames at different times of the day. (Bottom) the standard deviation of the estimated angle, σ_θ , per acquisition. C. The expected range of the system due to AT, at different turbulence conditions (defined by σ_θ). D. Normalized temporal correlations of angle-estimation, at the different times of the day (legend numbers denote acquisition times).

404

405 4. Discussion

406 We have presented and addressed the two most significant challenges of the method, which are
 407 1) dependence of distance estimation quality on object features and 2) degradation due to AT.
 408 Regarding the former, we have employed specific filtration in the cepstrum domain to help
 409 avoid generic erroneous results. Despite this, in special cases (e.g. no texture or a repetitive
 410 one) the proposed method is still susceptible to errors. Imperatively, such patterns are rare to
 411 find in typical real-world scenes, especially for dynamic objects, which are often the target for
 412 ranging applications (cars, planes, people, animals). The second challenge, AT, is the one we
 413 found to be the most influential on ranging performance. AT can be viewed as an inherent
 414 source of noise to the wavefront, which would degrade any passive ranging approach.
 415 Nevertheless, our results show that even under severe turbulence, good estimation precision
 416 (<5%) can be maintained at distances of several hundreds of meters. Clearly, under low
 417 turbulence conditions, the precision improves significantly, and in any case it can be further
 418 improved by employing multi-frame analysis. We speculate turbulence is the main reason for
 419 the lack of passive rangars at long distances, as it precludes achieving the pixel-scale accuracy
 420 often highly necessary for such instruments[2].

421 Several aspects of our methodology and implementation could be further optimized. One
422 of them is system construction; our embodiment was based on a custom 3D-printed mount,
423 which connects the optics to the telescope. The use of PLA for the integral mechanical part has
424 probably led the system to be subject to mild internal translations, requiring occasional
425 recalibration. In several occasions we have observed that calibration was off, leading to biased
426 results, especially when calibration could not be performed on-site. This meant the telescope
427 needed to be mounted and unloaded from a tripod and transported between sites, potentially
428 affecting the calibration. Clearly, stronger materials should be used for the setup, although a
429 robust alternative would be based on replacing the 4-f system by a large phase-mask placed in
430 front of the aperture. Such modification, however, comes with the challenge of producing such
431 a large phase mask; this may be impractical using commonly used fabrication such as
432 nanolithography. Nevertheless, recent developments in diffractive optical element fabrication
433 already enable simple custom-made phase masks on large scales, based on micron-scale 3D
434 printing[30]. The use of a large mask at the objective lens will also enable better flexibility in
435 choice of magnification (thus FOV) than shown in this work.

436 As for data analysis, we have employed an algorithmic approach based on simple CoM
437 analysis, and applied a neural network that was trained to handle cepstrums. While the analysis
438 scheme is relatively simple, it can be significantly improved by incorporation of object (feature)
439 detection, prior assumptions, usage of temporal information, Kalman filtering (for moving
440 objects) and more. Also, one of the main advantages of PSF engineering is the flexibility in
441 designing the system's PSF. The analysis pipeline can improve results significantly by
442 incorporating an initial optimal PSF-designing step[26]. The PSF can feature improved
443 compatibility to certain objects of interest (e.g. in an urban surrounding containing horizontal
444 and vertical lines, the PSF may benefit from extending in the diagonal directions), or increased
445 robustness to AT[31].
446

447 5. Conclusions

448 Experimentally demonstrated, PSF engineering can be employed for passive priorless ranging
449 over long distances, exceeding 1.5 km. The current thorough demonstration of the method's
450 validity holds the potential for a variety of technological extensions and applications; notably,
451 application-based PSF design, namely algorithmically learning the optimal PSF for different
452 ranging scenarios[21,26,32,33] is an exciting territory to be explored in this context.
453 Atmospheric turbulence has been found to be the prime source of error, and can be dealt with
454 by means of multi-frame analysis, constrained by precision and temporal resolution
455 requirements.

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459 **Data availability.** Data underlying the results presented in this paper may be obtained from the authors upon
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461 **Supplemental documents.** See [Supplement 1](#) and [supplementary videos S1-S5](#) for supporting content.
462

- 463 1. T. G. Phillips, N. Guenther, and P. R. McAree, "When the Dust Settles: The Four
464 Behaviors of LiDAR in the Presence of Fine Airborne Particulates," *J. F. Robot.*
465 **34**(5), 985–1009 (2017).
- 466 2. Y. Y. Schechner and N. Kiryati, "Depth from defocus vs. stereo: how different really
467 are they?," in *Proceedings. Fourteenth International Conference on Pattern*
468 *Recognition (Cat. No.98EX170)* (IEEE Comput. Soc, n.d.), **2**, pp. 1784–1786.
- 469 3. A. Orriordan, T. Newe, G. Dooly, and D. Toal, "Stereo Vision Sensing: Review of
470 existing systems," in *2018 12th International Conference on Sensing Technology*

- 471 (ICST) (IEEE, 2018), pp. 178–184.
- 472 4. F. Blais, "Review of 20 years of range sensor development," *J. Electron. Imaging*
473 **13**(1), 231 (2004).
- 474 5. B. Vanek, A. Zarandy, A. Hiba, P. Bauer, T. Tsuchiya, S. Nagai, and R. Mori,
475 *Technical Note D4 . 7 Preliminary Validation Results of Vision-Based Navigation*
476 *Techniques* (2019), **2018**(2018).
- 477 6. A. Saxena, S. Jamie, and A. Y. Ng, "Depth estimation using monocular and stereo
478 cues," *IJCAI Int. Jt. Conf. Artif. Intell.* 2197–2203 (2007).
- 479 7. S. G. Narasimhan and S. K. Nayar, "Vision and the Atmosphere," *Int. J. Comput. Vis.*
480 **48**(3), 233–254 (2002).
- 481 8. C. Wu, J. Ko, J. Coffaro, D. A. Paulson, J. R. Rzasa, L. C. Andrews, R. L. Phillips, R.
482 Crabbs, and C. C. Davis, "Using turbulence scintillation to assist object ranging from
483 a single camera viewpoint," *Appl. Opt.* **57**(9), 2177 (2018).
- 484 9. G. E. Johnson, E. R. Dowski, and W. T. Cathey, "Passive ranging through wave-front
485 coding: information and application," *Appl. Opt.* **39**(11), 1700 (2000).
- 486 10. A. Greengard, Y. Y. Schechner, and R. Piestun, "Depth from diffracted rotation,"
487 *Opt. Lett.* **31**(2), 181 (2006).
- 488 11. Y. Shechtman, S. J. Sahl, A. S. Backer, and W. E. Moerner, "Optimal Point Spread
489 Function Design for 3D Imaging," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **113**(13), 133902 (2014).
- 490 12. A. Levin, R. Fergus, F. Durand, and W. T. Freeman, "Image and depth from a
491 conventional camera with a coded aperture," *ACM Trans. Graph.* **26**(3), 70 (2007).
- 492 13. S. Quirin and R. Piestun, "Depth estimation and image recovery using broadband,
493 incoherent illumination with engineered point spread functions [Invited]," *Appl. Opt.*
494 **52**(1), A367 (2013).
- 495 14. R. Berlich, A. Bräuer, and S. Stallinga, "Single shot approach for three-dimensional
496 imaging with double-helix point spread functions," in *Imaging and Applied Optics*
497 *2016* (OSA, 2016), p. CTh1D.4.
- 498 15. S. Tucker, W. T. Cathey, and E. Dowski, Jr., "Extended depth of field and aberration
499 control for inexpensive digital microscope systems," *Opt. Express* **4**(11), 467 (1999).
- 500 16. J. Broeken, B. Rieger, and S. Stallinga, "Simultaneous measurement of position and
501 color of single fluorescent emitters using diffractive optics," *Opt. Lett.* **39**(11), 3352
502 (2014).
- 503 17. Y. Shechtman, L. E. Weiss, A. S. Backer, M. Y. Lee, and W. E. Moerner,
504 "Multicolour localization microscopy by point-spread-function engineering," *Nat.*
505 *Photonics* **10**(9), 590–594 (2016).
- 506 18. E. Hershko, L. E. Weiss, T. Michaeli, and Y. Shechtman, "Multicolor localization
507 microscopy and point-spread-function engineering by deep learning," *Opt. Express*
508 **27**(5), 6158 (2019).
- 509 19. N. Opatovski, Y. Shalev Ezra, L. E. Weiss, B. Ferdman, R. Orange-Kedem, and Y.
510 Shechtman, "Multiplexed PSF Engineering for Three-Dimensional Multicolor
511 Particle Tracking," *Nano Lett.* **21**(13), 5888–5895 (2021).
- 512 20. V. Sitzmann, S. Diamond, Y. Peng, X. Dun, S. Boyd, W. Heidrich, F. Heide, and G.
513 Wetzstein, "End-to-end optimization of optics and image processing for achromatic
514 extended depth of field and super-resolution imaging," *ACM Trans. Graph.* **37**(4), 1–
515 13 (2018).
- 516 21. X. Dun, H. Ikoma, G. Wetzstein, Z. Wang, X. Cheng, and Y. Peng, "Learned
517 rotationally symmetric diffractive achromat for full-spectrum computational
518 imaging," *Optica* **7**(8), 913 (2020).
- 519 22. S. R. P. Pavani and R. Piestun, "High-efficiency rotating point spread functions," *Opt.*
520 *Express* **16**(5), 3484 (2008).
- 521 23. D. G. Childers, D. P. Skinner, and R. C. Kemerait, "The cepstrum: A guide to
522 processing," *Proc. IEEE* **65**(10), 1428–1443 (1977).

- 523 24. J. K. Lee, M. Kabrisky, M. E. Oxley, S. K. Rogers, and D. W. Ruck, "The complex
524 cepstrum applied to two-dimensional images," *Pattern Recognit.* **26**(10), 1579–1592
525 (1993).
- 526 25. B. Ferdman, E. Nehme, L. E. Weiss, R. Orange, O. Alalouf, and Y. Shechtman,
527 "VIPR: vectorial implementation of phase retrieval for fast and accurate microscopic
528 pixel-wise pupil estimation," *Opt. Express* **28**(7), 10179 (2020).
- 529 26. E. Nehme, D. Freedman, R. Gordon, B. Ferdman, L. E. Weiss, O. Alalouf, T. Naor,
530 R. Orange, T. Michaeli, and Y. Shechtman, "DeepSTORM3D: dense 3D localization
531 microscopy and PSF design by deep learning," *Nat. Methods* **17**(7), 734–740 (2020).
- 532 27. H. C. van Assen, M. Egmont-Petersen, and J. H. C. Reiber, "Accurate object
533 localization in gray level images using the center of gravity measure: accuracy versus
534 precision," *IEEE Trans. Image Process.* **11**(12), 1379–1384 (2002).
- 535 28. J. R. Fienup, "Reconstruction of an object from the modulus of its Fourier transform,"
536 *Opt. Lett.* Vol. 3, Issue 1, pp. 27-29 **3**(1), 27–29 (1978).
- 537 29. Y. Xu, Q. Ye, A. Hoorfar, and G. Meng, "Extrapolative phase retrieval based on a
538 hybrid of PhaseCut and alternating projection techniques," *Opt. Lasers Eng.* **121**, 96–
539 103 (2019).
- 540 30. R. Orange-Kedem, E. Nehme, L. E. Weiss, B. Ferdman, O. Alalouf, N. Opatovski,
541 and Y. Shechtman, "3D printable diffractive optical elements by liquid immersion,"
542 *Nat. Commun.* (2021).
- 543 31. X. Liu and J. Pu, "Investigation on the scintillation reduction of elliptical vortex
544 beams propagating in atmospheric turbulence," *Opt. Express* **19**(27), 26444 (2011).
- 545 32. V. Sitzmann, S. Diamond, Y. Peng, X. Dun, S. Boyd, W. Heidrich, F. Heide, and G.
546 Wetzstein, "End-to-end optimization of optics and image processing for achromatic
547 extended depth of field and super-resolution imaging," *ACM Trans. Graph.* **37**(4), 1–
548 13 (2018).
- 549 33. E. Nehme, B. Ferdman, L. E. Weiss, T. Naor, D. Freedman, T. Michaeli, and Y.
550 Shechtman, "Learning Optimal Wavefront Shaping for Multi-Channel Imaging,"
551 *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.* **43**(7), 2179–2192 (2021).
- 552